

DEVELOPMENT OF A SELF-HEALING INTERPHASE FOR STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

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FULL PAPER

INTRODUCTION

- Fiber-reinforced polymer composites: matrix + fibers, separated by the **interphase** where the two phases interact, dictating the **properties of the final component**.
- Self-healing interphase:** interphase able to **restore** the interactions between the two phases if subjected to heat.
- The healing process **extends the service life of the composites**.
- Aim of the work:** development of a **coating** for glass fibers made of **Polycaprolactone (PCL)** to provide the healing of the interphase with an epoxy matrix. The glass fibers are provided both with and without the compatible superficial sizing.

EXPERIMENTAL

RESULTS

Morphological analysis (FESEM) of PCL coated GF₁ / GF₂

Mechanical (microdebonding) analysis of PCL coated GF₁ / GF₂ (30V, 60s)

CONCLUSIONS

PCL nanoparticles deposition on the glass fibers surface provides **homogeneous and high-quality coatings** that allow a **50% recovery of the initial mechanical properties of the composites** (in terms of interfacial strength, IFSS), delaying the end of life of the component. The presence of the compatible silane sizing does not influence the healing mechanism.

REFERENCES

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